

Microstructure and activity of platinumized CdS-Al₂O₃ photocatalysts for reduction of water to hydrogen by visible light[†]

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Alumina supported Pt-CdS is an effective photocatalyst for the reduction of water to hydrogen using visible light. The activity is dependent on the method of incorporation of platinum on the catalyst. The catalysts were characterized by XRD, XPS, H₂ chemisorption, temperature programmed oxidation and optical spectroscopy. The results show that the band gap of CdS has no correlation with the activity. Crystallite size of CdS and the nature of contact between alumina and CdS, however, affect the activity. Platinum on the surface of the catalyst is in the form of Pt-PtS_x.

Alumina supported cadmium sulfide has been reported to be an active photocatalyst for reduction of water to hydrogen¹⁻⁶ in presence of visible light. However, it is also likely that the photogenerated electrons and holes, instead of taking part into the reaction, may recombine and produce only heat. Therefore, the efficiency of a photocatalyst depends on the relative rates of generation and recombination of electrons and holes. The rate of recombination is substantially high on most of the semiconductors. We reported earlier⁴ that the incorporation of alumina to CdS results into formation of a heterojunction that prevents electron-hole recombination. Incorporation of Group VIII metals, like platinum, also suppresses the rate of recombination. Uchihara *et al.*⁷ reported that when platinum is deposited on CdS, the Fermi level of CdS moves towards a more positive potential, leading to a stronger band bending, and hence enhanced photocatalytic reaction. Apart from that, the Group VIII metals are also good hydrogenation-dehydrogenation catalysts. Therefore, these metals when present on the surface, would also catalyze the reaction, $H^+ + e^- \rightarrow \frac{1}{2} H_2$, and thereby increase the hydrogen evolution rate and the quantum efficiency. Aspnes and Heller⁸ on the other hand reported that the deposition of a metal on the surface on an *n*-type semiconductor results in the formation of a metal-semiconductor junction, or Schottky barrier, prevents electrons from reaching the catalytically active metal where proton reduction should be taking place. Thus, hydrogen generation is determined by the irradiance and the barrier height created between the semiconductor and the metal. They reported⁸ that platinum reacts with CdS to form

platinum sulfide. Thus the contact is not Pt/CdS, but a hydrogen-insensitive contact (PtS_x-Cd-CdS)/CdS.

Many methods of platinum deposition have been reported in the literature and it has been observed that activity of the catalysts depends on the details of the preparation techniques⁹⁻¹⁶. However, a detailed study on the microstructure of catalysts and its effect on their catalytic activities is not well-documented in the literature.

In the present study, platinum was incorporated on CdS-Al₂O₃ catalysts by different techniques. Activities of these catalysts for reduction of water to hydrogen were measured. Catalysts were characterized to develop the inter-relation amongst preparation variables, catalysts microstructure and activity.

Results and discussion

Activity :

Activities of the platinum incorporated catalysts are reported in Table 1. The catalyst which was prepared by

Table 1. Activity and physical properties of catalysis

Catalyst no.	H ₂ evolved* in 2 h (ml at NTP)	Mean crystallite size, nm	Platinum exposed %	Band gap of CdS eV
1	4.0	8.3	8.4	2.32
2	13.0	5.5	4.0	2.32
3	0.0	5.4	0.0	2.33
4	2.7	7.3	0.0	2.32

*per g of CdS.

[†]Dedicated to Professor R. P. Rastogi.

impregnation with a solution of chloroplatinic acid and reduced at 473 K in hydrogen (catalyst-2) has an activity that is more than double of another catalyst (not reported here) which was prepared by the same technique but did not contain platinum. But, as seen from Table 1, if a higher temperature is employed for the decomposition of chloroplatinic acid, the activity of the resulting catalyst (catalyst-1) drops down. Catalyst-4 was prepared by the same technique as catalyst-1. The only difference was that in the case of catalyst-4, platinum was first incorporated on alumina followed by CdS whereas the order was reversed for catalyst-1. It is observed from the result that catalyst-4 also shows a lower activity. It is further observed that platinum deposited on CdS by photoreduction (catalyst-3) does not show any activity. It is relevant to add that bare CdS, prepared from the same technique as catalyst-3, shows an activity of 2 ml H₂ per g CdS in 2 h. Thus, the incorporation of platinum had adversely affected the activity of CdS in catalyst-3.

It is worthwhile to mention (and as discussed above) that a number of contradictory results have been reported in the literature on the effect of platinum incorporation on the semiconductor surfaces. In the present study also, it is observed that the incorporation of platinum may or may not lead to a better activity. The crucial factor, however, appears to be the method of incorporation of platinum to the catalysts.

XRD studies :

The X-ray diffraction patterns of catalysts were obtained and the *d*-value (interplaner spacing) for each peak was calculated, and peaks were identified as those of the hexagonal phase of CdS and γ -Al₂O₃. Peaks corresponding to platinum were not observed in any of the diffraction patterns. This may be due to very low concentrations of platinum in the catalysts. The mean crystallite sizes of CdS in the catalysts were estimated from the full width at half intensity of the peaks and are given in Table 1. It is observed that the mean crystallite sizes are larger in those catalysts which were subjected to higher temperatures during the preparation stage. It is also observed that the activity could be correlated to some extent with the crystallite size of CdS, i.e. its dispersion. Catalyst-2 shows the highest activity and the highest dispersion of CdS. Catalyst-1 and catalyst-4 have lower dispersions of CdS and also have low activities. However, catalyst-3 has the same degree of dispersion as catalyst-2 but catalyst-3 does not show any activity. Similarly, catalyst-1 and catalyst-4 have similar dispersions, yet catalyst-4 shows a lower activity compared to catalyst-1.

Optical absorption studies :

The absorbance spectra of various catalysts were recorded in the wavelength range 350–700 nm. The absorbance in-

creased sharply with a decrease in the wavelength below ~550 nm and gradually tapered to a plateau. The band gap of CdS in different catalysts was calculated by the reported method¹⁷. For each catalyst, $(\alpha h\nu)^2$ vs $h\nu$ was plotted. The intercept on the *x*-coordinate gives the band gap of the semiconductor. The band gap of CdS in all the catalysts was observed to be the same, i.e. 2.32 eV (Table 1) which is very close to the reported value of ~2.42 eV for CdS¹⁸. Therefore, the incorporation of Pt does not affect the band gap of cadmium sulfide. Hence, the observed difference in the activities of platinum-incorporated catalysts can not be correlated to the band gap of CdS in the catalysts.

Temperature programmed oxidation studies :

It has been discussed earlier⁴ that for a better activity of alumina-supported cadmium sulfide photocatalysts, there should be a chemical interaction between cadmium sulfide and alumina. Such a chemical interaction reduces the probability of the recombination of photogenerated electrons and holes. It has also been shown that the oxidation of alumina-supported cadmium sulfide takes place at two different temperatures, i.e. 950 and 1000 K. It is concluded that cadmium sulfide, which has chemically interacted with alumina, gets oxidized at a lower temperature of 950 K compared to cadmium sulfide uninteracted with alumina and gets oxidized at 1000 K.

Temperature programmed oxidation of platinum-incorporated CdS-Al₂O₃ catalysts was also carried out in the present study. The results are shown in Fig. 1. It is

Fig. 1. Temperature programmed oxidation profile of catalysts.

observed from the figure that for each of the catalysts nos. 1, 2 and 4, there are two oxidations peaks. The peaks are well resolved in catalyst-2. The ratio of the area of lower temperature peak to that of higher temperature peak was calculated for each peak. The ratio is nearly equal for catalyst-1 and catalyst-2 but a lower value was observed for catalyst-3. This observation is in agreement with the conclusions drawn earlier⁴ that the impregnation of alumina hydrogel with cadmium sulfate solution results in a chemical interaction between the two. Catalyst-1 and catalyst-2 which showed greater interactions, were prepared by the impregnation of hydrogel. On the other hand, in the preparation of catalyst-4 the hydrogel was subjected to a high temperature of 673 K prior to the impregnation with cadmium sulfate solution. The heat treatment would dry the hydrogel and consequently a lower degree of the chemical interaction was observed in catalyst-4. Catalyst-3 did not contain alumina, therefore such an interaction is non-existent.

Therefore, the lower activity of catalyst-4 is attributed to the absence of the chemical interaction to the extent as observed in catalyst-1 and catalyst-2. However, the difference in the activities of catalyst-1 and catalyst-2 could not be explained. Both of them exhibited chemical interactions of the same degree, still the activity of catalyst-2 was observed to be much greater than that of catalyst-1.

Hydrogen chemisorption studies :

Hydrogen chemisorption studies were carried out to study the dispersion of platinum on the surface of the catalysts. Percentage of platinum exposed, i.e. the percentage of total platinum atoms present on the surface of the catalysts, in each catalyst, was calculated. The results are shown in Table 1. The values are seen to be rather low. This indicates that either the crystallites of platinum are large, or a fraction of platinum has gone inside the bulk of the catalyst, or it has been converted into its compound during the preparation stage of the catalysts.

It is observed from Table 1 that percentage of platinum exposed is zero for catalyst-3 and catalyst-4. The analysis of the surfaces of catalysts (*cf.* XPS results given below) shows that platinum (either as metal or its compound) is present in catalyst-3 but not in catalyst-4. Since, in the preparation of catalyst-4, platinum was incorporated first followed by CdS, it is likely that platinum has gone into the bulk of the catalyst. Whereas on the basis of the combined results of the H₂ chemisorption studies and XPS analysis, it is concluded that the platinum incorporated in catalyst-3 has changed to its compound. The possibility of formation of platinum sulfide by solid state reaction between CdS and platinum has been indicated by Aspnes and Heller⁸.

It has been discussed earlier that incorporation of platinum metal in CdS/Al₂O₃ as well as a chemical interaction between CdS and alumina lead to a better charge separation and improved activity. Since both these phenomena are absent in catalyst-3, it showed a negligible activity for hydrogen production. However, in catalyst-4, though there is no platinum metal on the surface, the temperature programmed oxidation studies have shown that there exists a chemical interaction between CdS and alumina to some extent. Therefore, the prevention of charge recombination is likely and consequently catalyst-4 shows some activity for hydrogen production.

It is in order to mention that though catalyst-3 did not contain alumina but it had platinum incorporated on the surface, which also caused the charge separation. Still this catalyst did not show any activity. Its activity was even worse than bare CdS. This may be due to the inactivation of CdS during preparation stage using UV-radiation.

It is further observed from Table 1 that catalyst-1 has a higher percentage of platinum exposed than catalyst-2. The temperature programmed oxidation has shown the same degree of chemical interaction between CdS and alumina in both the catalysts. Still the activity of catalyst-1 is lower than that of catalyst-2. It may be recalled that XRD studies had shown that crystallite size of CdS in catalyst-2 was smaller than that in catalyst-1. Since, a smaller crystallite size, i.e. a better dispersion of CdS should yield a superior activity, therefore, the improved activity of catalyst-2 compared to catalyst-1 is attributed to the better dispersion of CdS in catalyst-2.

XPS studies :

X-Ray photoelectron spectra of catalysts were obtained to characterize the surfaces of the catalysts. Carbon with the binding energy of 285.0 eV was taken as the reference. The spectra are shown in Figs. 2 and 3. It is observed from Fig. 2 that peaks of Cd ($3d_{5/2}$) appear between 404.2 (catalyst-1) and 405.4 eV (catalyst-2). The reported value of Cd ($3d_{5/2}$) in 2+ oxidation state (CdS) is 405.0 eV. Since, rather broad peaks were obtained in the present study probably due to dispersion of CdS on a support, it was difficult to locate precisely the positions of the highest intensities. Therefore, the observed variations in the binding energy are not considered significant and it is concluded that cadmium is present on the surface in 2+ oxidation state only. It may be recalled that the XRD analysis has shown the presence of cadmium as CdS only; therefore, this result is in conformity with the XRD results.

An analysis of the spectra (Fig. 3) of Pt ($4f_{7/2}$) shows that the peaks are obtained at 72.8, 73.8 and 73.0 eV for

catalysts 1, 2 and 3, respectively. The observed difference in the binding energies is not considered significant for the reason stated above that due to the broadness of the peaks

Fig. 2. XPS spectra of Cd (3d) in catalysts.

Fig. 3. XPS spectra of Pt ($4f_{7/2}$) in catalysts. No Pt peak was observed in catalyst-4.

the determination of the position of highest intensity was difficult. However, the observed values do not match with either of the standard values of Pt ($4f_{7/2}$) reported for 0, +2 and +4 oxidation states, i.e. 71.0 (Pt metal), 74.0 (PtO) and 74.8 (PtO₂) eV, respectively. Since the peaks are rather broad, it is likely that they are not resolved for each of the oxidation states of platinum. In other words, the observed peaks are resultants of the peaks corresponding to different oxidation states of platinum. It has been discussed above that low dispersion of platinum observed from chemisorption studies indicates the presence of platinum in higher oxidation states. Therefore, it is concluded that platinum on the surface of the catalysts is present as platinum metal and platinum sulfide. i.e. the catalysts contain Pt-PtS-CdS-Al₂O₃. Further, the chemisorption studies reveal negligible dispersion of platinum metal in the cases of catalyst-3 and catalyst-4. However, the XPS results show presence of platinum on the surface of catalyst-3. Therefore, it is concluded that platinum in catalyst-3 is largely present as platinum sulfide. On the other hand, XPS does not show presence of any platinum on the surface of catalyst-4. Therefore, as visualized earlier, it is concluded that platinum incorporated in catalyst-4 has gone inside the bulk of the catalysts. Thus, the lower activities of catalyst-3 and catalyst-4 are attributed to the negligible concentration of platinum of the surfaces of these catalysts. It is in order to mention that Thewissen *et al.*¹⁸, Rufus *et al.*^{19,20} reported that platinum sulfide acts as hole transferring agent and thereby causing the charge separation for a better activity. Platinum metal, on the other hand, transfers electrons to itself and prevents the recombination of the photogenerated electrons and holes. Further, since the reduction of water to hydrogen is mediated by electrons, therefore, the presence of platinum rather than platinum sulfide appears to be more desirable for a better activity. Also, platinum acts as a catalyst for the reaction, $H^+ + e^- \rightarrow 1/2 H_2$. Therefore, the presence of platinum metal on the surfaces of catalyst-1 and catalyst-2 imparts a better catalytic activity to these two catalysts compared to catalyst-3 and catalyst-4. Further, compared to catalyst-1, the better activity of catalyst-2 is attributed to the higher dispersion of CdS in catalyst-2.

Experimental

Catalyst preparation : A high surface area aluminium hydroxide gel¹⁵ was prepared by neutralizing a concentrated solution of aluminium nitrate with ammonia at pH 9 and at 303 K. The hydrogel was aged for 48 h and then washed with distilled water until it was free from nitrate ions. The following catalysts were prepared. All the chemicals used were of the A.R. grade.

Catalyst-1 : An ammonical solution of cadmium sulfate was mixed with aluminium hydroxide hydrogel and chloroplatinic acid such that the weight ratio of the final catalyst was Al₂O₃ : CdS = 2 : 1 and platinum was 0.1% of the cadmium sulfide by weight. The mixture was dried over a water-bath and then in an air oven at 383 K. The resulting mass was heated at 673 K in an atmosphere of nitrogen to decompose the chloroplatinic acid followed by reaction with H₂S gas at the same temperature.

Catalyst 2 : It was prepared in the same manner as catalyst-1 except that, instead of decomposing chloroplatinic acid at 673 K, it was reduced by hydrogen at 473 K. The reaction with H₂S was also carried out at 473 K.

Catalyst-3 : In this case, chloroplatinic acid was photo-reduced by using UV radiation¹⁶. CdS was first prepared by reacting granules of cadmium sulfate with H₂S at 473 K in a fixed bed reactor. The granules were crushed to powder. The powder was mixed with the requisite volume of chloroplatinic acid. The resulting mixture was taken in a quartz glass photoreactor (200 ml) and 0.25 M solution of acetic acid (90 ml) buffered at pH 4.5 was also added to it. The mixture was kept stirred by sparging nitrogen gas and was irradiated by UV lamps in a Perfit (India) photochemical reactor assembly for 30 min. The resulting mass was then separated by filtration, washed with water and then dried at 383 K. Alumina was not used in this catalyst to support CdS.

Catalyst 4 : It was prepared by impregnation of aluminium hydroxide hydrogel with chloroplatinic acid. The mixture was dried over a water-bath and then heated at 673 K in N₂ to decompose chloroplatinic acid to platinum. The resulting mass was further impregnated with an ammonical solution of CdSO₄, dried over a water-bath and then in an air-oven at 383 K. The dried mass was finally reacted with H₂S gas at 473 K.

Experimental setup : Activity and deactivation of the catalyst were studied in a batch reactor. The details of the reactor are given elsewhere¹. The catalyst (2 g; 200 mesh) was suspended in aqueous solution (250 ml) of concentration 0.01 M with respect to Na₂S and 0.004 M with respect to Na₂SO₃. The solution was kept stirred with a magnetic stirrer. The pH of the solution was maintained at 8.6 by adding requisite drops of 1 M NaOH and 1 M acetic acid. Prior to irradiation, the reaction mixture was purged with nitrogen in order to remove dissolved gases. The temperature was set to a desired level by varying the input voltage to the heating cord. A 150W Philips halogen – tungsten lamp was used as the light source. The gas evolved was

collected in the burette by the water displacement technique. The reproducibility of data was tested in separate runs and the data reported represent the average values.

The collected gas was analyzed to an online gas chromatograph (Nucon Engineers, India ; Model 5700) using a 5 Å molecular sieve column and a thermal conductivity detector (TCD). Gas samples were taken in a six-way gas sampling valve having a sample loop of 1.0 ml. A comparison of the retention time of the only peak that appeared on the chromatogram with the standard confirmed that the gas was only hydrogen.

Characterization studies : For the identification of phases and estimation of crystallite sizes X-ray diffraction (XRD) studies were carried out on a Philips 1710 X-ray diffractometer with a Cu-K_α target of radiation wavelength 1.542 Å. X-Ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) studies were carried out on a Perkin-Elmer φ 1800 spectrometer using a MgK_α target for studying the oxidation states of platinum and cadmium on the catalysis surface. Carbon was used as an internal source for calibration. The dispersion of platinum was studied by the chemisorption of hydrogen gas (5% hydrogen in argon gas) at 333 K using a Micromeritics Pulse Chemisorb 2705. Prior to adsorption, the samples were heated *in situ* to 473 K in a flow of argon gas for 5 h. The temperature-programmed-oxidation of cadmium sulfide in the catalysts was carried out to investigate any strong interaction established between CdS and alumina using a Micromeritics Pulse Chemisorb 2705 with temperature-programmed-reduction/oxidation unit. Samples were placed in a quartz tube and heated at a programmed rate of 15 K per 60 s. A mixed of 5.0% oxygen in argon was allowed to flow over the samples at a rate of 0.5 ml s⁻¹. Prior to oxidation, samples were heated at 900 K for 5 h in an inert environment of flowing argon gas. Any change in the concentration of oxygen was detected by the thermal conductivity detector of the instrument. Thus peak profile in terms of consumption of oxygen vs temperature was obtained for each catalyst. A Shimadzu 160A UV-visible spectrophotometer was used to study the optical absorbance characteristics of catalysts. Powdered samples were made into a paste with nujol and mounted as a thin film on a quartz plate. A similar plate with only a film of nujol was used as the reference. The band gap of the catalysts was also obtained using the equations given by Bube¹⁷.

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